

D3.5 Second report on mapping of EOSC prospective service providers and candidate services

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Abstract:

This deliverable describes results of the additional mapping of EOSC prospective service providers and candidate services coming from the Nordic and Baltic countries. Services are analysed with aggregated results presented in this deliverable.

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Executive Summary

This document is a deliverable of the EOSC-Nordic project supported by the European Commission under Horizon 2020. The deliverable is the work of *Work Package 3 - Support to prospective EOSC service providers (WP3)*.

In this report, we used the infrastructure service mapping approach that we developed in D3.2. Our aim was to assess the existing services and support them to fulfil EOSC requirements and help with EOSC onboarding of services.

The services were analysed using the service inventory template developed in EOSC-Nordic as summarised in [D3.2](#). We augmented this template by adding mapping criteria which help to analyse services in terms of cross-border consumption, cross-border collaboration, commercial usage, academic use and access policies.

Furthermore, results of the assessment were summarised and analysed, allowing us to improve the overall service mapping process. We intend to disseminate our summarized findings and outcomes to a wider audience via the EOSC-Nordic web site¹.

This deliverable describes results of both the initial report and the additional mapping of EOSC prospective service providers and candidate services coming from the Nordic and Baltic countries. In order to do an additional discovery of services offered by national research infrastructure providers that participate in the EOSC-Nordic project, this deliverable adopts and extends the service inventory template developed for D3.2² to capture information about services. It provides a list of additional EOSC prospective service providers and candidate services and reports on the work done to integrate the first set of services and the result of this integration. 60 services from 8 countries/areas were captured.

Summary of results

The services mapped are mainly within five categories - compute, data storage, data analysis, data management and data sharing (e.g., data access & data dissemination for reuse), and they account for about 97% of all services in the inventory. The services are aimed mainly towards researchers, and they can be accessed remotely or virtually. The cross-border concept was found to be complicated, since most of the service providers that provided input to the service inventory are bound by national funding constraints and are providing services in the context of national research and education. Some services are available to the research projects that get national funding, and as such the projects can be for cross-border use. Few services are cross-border, but the number of services is slowly increasing. There are examples of cross border collaboration, but they are mainly financed cross-border with a top-down perspective. Identification and assessment of the drivers and inhibitors for cross-border consumption observed by the services seems highly relevant and have been investigated further in a previous deliverable³. We have found that service's main drive consists mainly of national interest and laws/regulations and financial input. This makes harmonization more difficult.

Introduction

This deliverable is an extended report of [D3.2: Mapping of EOSC prospective service providers and candidate services](#). It provides a list of additional EOSC prospective service providers and candidate services and

¹ <https://eosc-nordic.eu/>

² <https://eosc-nordic.eu/kh-material/deliverable-3-2-first-report-on-mapping-of-eosc-prospective-service-providers-and-d-candidate-services/>

³ <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/kh-material/d2-2-cross-border-collaboration-models-the-nordic-experience/>

reports on the work done to integrate the first set of services. We paid particular attention to IT-services which have the potential to operate on a cross-border basis. Interactions with service providers were organised by this task's members and services are described following the agreed EOSC templates with a view to integrating them into the EOSC portal.

This deliverable provides an additional summary of the mapping as well as an analysis of the results for the discovered services. Note that the concrete steps for supporting the maturity level of services is outside the scope of this document since this deliverable focuses mainly on the cross-border perspective.

This document is structured in the following manner:

- The Section *Service inventory* describes the approach used for the mapping and also summarises the coverage of the identified services.
- The *Results of the second round of assessment* section presents the mapping that was applied to the identified services, describes the assessment process and provides aggregated analysis of the outcome. For the sake of brevity as well as privacy considerations, this deliverable does not include analysis results for the individual services.
- *Conclusions, discussion and next steps* describe how we plan to use the outcome of this deliverable.

We have taken into account the *Recommendation 4* of the midterm review (EOSC Maturity Model Classifications and Self-Assessment):

“The checklist in WP3 provides a good basis for assessing the EOSC readiness of open science services. From the demonstration during the review, it is also clear that the criteria have been classified in different categories based on their importance as EOSC readiness enablers. It is recommended to extend this work through providing insights on possible levels of progressive maturity. The consortium should consider clustering EOSC services in different maturity levels. In-line with the approach followed, the project should provide tools/forms enabling providers to perform a self-assessment of their EOSC readiness”.

Service inventory

One of the objectives of WP3 is to identify and support integration into the EOSC portal of services offered to researchers by service providers in the Nordic-Baltic region. The effort of doing the service discovery is of importance for further work, on the assessment of these services according to the service inventory.

Another important anticipated outcome of the service discovery exercise is to create a service inventory and to analyse it to identify a baseline, differences and overlaps of the national service portfolios offered to researchers. This can be further used to identify opportunities for experience and knowledge sharing, interoperability of services in international service provision scenarios and collaboration in order to tackle common issues and challenges.

We deem services which support cross-border usage as attractive candidates for EOSC. In addition to collecting information on these new attributes for the services we mapped in D3.2, we added more candidate services from Nordic and Baltic service providers.

Service inventory template

In order to assess the services, we use the updated service inventory template previously developed for WP3 and described in deliverable D3.2.

The service inventory template is now adopted as the standard scheme for the representation of service-related information in the EOSC catalogue. The template defines attributes and their potential values. The goal of the template is "to collect information in a systematic, consistent way which forms a solid basis for subsequent analysis.

Over the course of EOSC Nordic project, it became clear that while technically cross-border usage for most of the mapped services is not a problem, policy-wise services might not be eligible to be shared. To address that in the analysis, the following attributes were added in this mapping:

- **Cross-border consumption is allowed:** The service supports users affiliated with organizations in another country.
- **Cross-border collaboration is allowed:** Users have to be from the same country, but collaborators can be from others.
- **Commercial usage is allowed:** The service can be used outside of the academia context.
- **Free for academic usage (in other countries):** Service is provided for free for eligible users in the country of the service consumer.
- **Free for academic usage (in the same country):** Service is provided for free for eligible users in the country of the service provider.

Selection for EOSC candidate services

The selection includes IT-services and services are not excluded on the sole basis of not being able to provide cross-border services. We aimed to also have diversity in the service provider selection, in order to have awareness of the diversity of different services available in the countries included in the inventory.

Results of the second round of assessment

As a major aspect of our work towards D3.5, we identified the need to analyse cross-border attributes of services. The goal of this task is to discover prospective service providers and services that could be offered across borders using the EOSC platform. We analyzed the differences and overlaps of the national services.

The service inventory template provides a tool for describing the attributes of services based on different characteristics spread across categories and is meant to evaluate the readiness of a service for inclusion into the EOSC Catalogue.

As WP3 participants represent different national perspectives and networks from the Nordic and Baltic countries, we were able to get a sample to populate this service inventory. A selection of mature services already in production offered by WP3 participants' organisations as well as communities and other prominent research service providers were mapped. Regarding the reliability of data, the input was provided by service providers themselves in what can be considered a self-assessment manner.

As a result, the inventory includes: 62 services from 8 countries/areas, see figure 1:

- Norway (7), Estonia (13), Latvia (5), Sweden (13), Iceland (4), Finland (7), and Denmark (11), and Nordic/European (2). Lithuania did not provide updates to the mapping and as such Lithuanian services are excluded from this deliverable.

Service provider country

Figure 1: Service provider amount by country.

Most of the service providers that provided input to the service inventory are bounded by national funding and are providing services in the context of national research and education. Some services, though, are available to the research projects that get funding from EU and the industry/private sources and as such the projects can be international, cross-border use.

New services added

In this deliverable we also aimed to include new services. The following is a summary of the new services.

New services from Estonia:

- New services from Estonia were chosen to bring out the diversity in terms of categories and service providers. New services covered fields like data repositories, AAI, data management and information systems.

New services from Denmark:

- New services from Denmark were chosen to broaden the service diversities. The new services include HPC, repositories and a specialized transcription service.

New services from Finland: Finland has two new data services

- The first is used for finding and accessing data.
- The second one is for data access, curation, long-term preservation and dissemination for reuse.

New services from Latvia:

- New tools for data analysis, data management/curation service being developed by the private sector (university spin-off).

New services from Sweden:

- Cloud and edge compute and storage resources.
- Large-scale analysis of written collections used to develop language models and work with artificial intelligence.
- Research and digitisation project.
- Data repository for generated scientific data set.
- Data analysis as a service portal - Compute service in production.

New services from Iceland:

- Data service for social science data. It is a data repository and is available for open access.

The old and new services are summarized in this table:

	Norway	Estonia	Latvia	Sweden	Iceland	Finland	Nordic/ European	Denmark	Total
Number of old services	7	3	2	7	1	5	0	8	33
Number of new services	0	10	3	5	1	2	2	3	26

Service categories

The five largest service categories are compute (19 services), data storage (13 services), data analysis (8 services) data management (6 services), data (7 services), security & identity (5 services). Compute services make up the single most frequent category with about 30%, while data storage is about 21 % of all the services. The remaining services are related to compute data (1 service), consultancy & support (1), operations & infrastructure management services (1 service) and software (1 service). Compute, data storage, data analysis, data management and data account for about 93.6 % of all services in the inventory.

Figure 2 below shows the distribution in the service category:

Service Category

Figure 2: Service Category.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of service categories among the participating 62 services.

Figure 3: Service Category by country.

The service categories from the different countries are:

- The service category from Iceland includes compute and data. The compute category is connected to an Icelandic HPC and the data storage category is an open access data storage for social sciences.

- Norwegian services include two HPC systems, two services for storing and archiving of data, one service for data analytics, a service for creating data management plans, and a service for storing and processing sensitive data. All services are open to any field of science.
- There is a wide range of service types from Denmark, everything from compute services, a repository, DMP service, security to a consultancy service. The services are managed by the Danish NREN and three universities.
- Estonia has five different categories: data storage, data management, data analysis, compute and security & identity.
- Finland has four different categories: data analysis, compute, data storage, and data (finding and accessing data, curation of data, long term preservation of data, data access and dissemination for reuse).
- Sweden has five types of categories: data storage, compute, data analysis, security & identity, the service providing software is now end of life.
- Latvia covers different types of services.

Target users

The main target group for all services are researchers with 80%. The remaining target groups include service/resource providers, research communities, and research organisations, see figure 4.

Target Users

Figure 4: Target Users.

The following figure (figure 5) shows the distribution of the different countries and the kind of users a service is provided for:

Target Users & Countries

Figure 5: Target Users by country.

- The target users from Iceland are non-commercial users, researchers and academics
- In Norway the majority of users are from research institutions. However, recently efforts to attract commercial users have been increased, and there are some commercial pilot users. The HPC resources have also been extensively used by the Folkehelseinstituttet (public health institute) for simulations concerned with the spreading of the Coronavirus.
- The target users in Denmark cover a wide range of user groups. They range from researchers, research projects and research institutions.
- Target users in Estonia divided researchers (10), research communities (2) and research organisations (1).
- Similar to Norway, many users in Finland come from academic and research institutions. Commercial usage may be allowed with some limitations.
- Latvia’s primary target users are researchers or research groups.
- The target users in Sweden are mainly researchers, with one smaller service offering services to research groups.

Cross-border categories, Commercial usage & free for academic usage

Cross-border consumption is a complex matter. 56.5% of the services answered “yes” to the question “Is cross border consumption allowed”, while 33.9% answered “no”. The remaining services added more information on how the services can be used for cross-border consumption. Figure 6 below shows the complexity in the question.

Cross-border consumption is allowed

Figure 6: Cross-border consumption.

Figure 7 below summarizes the answers from the different countries:

Cross-border consumption is allowed

Figure 7: Cross-border consumption by country

- The cross-border categories from Iceland are as follows: data storage is open to everyone, but the HPC service is not available for cross-border collaboration.

- Cross-border consumption is allowed on Norwegian HPC systems via the PRACE DECI Access scheme⁴. Also, the easyDMP service as well as TSD (service for sensitive data) is allowed for cross-border consumption. The other services are not allowed for cross-border consumption.
- The cross-border properties are extremely varied when it comes to cross-border categories and collaboration in the Danish services. In general, cross-border consumption is very low and mostly occurs in spite of the institutional or national setup of the service.
- Estonian compute services are available for cross-border usage, but some national data storage services are meant for use only by Estonians. In total, 8 out of 13 services can be used cross-border. Cross-border collaboration is available for all listed services.
- Cross-border usage is not allowed for most of the Finnish services (4 out of 7), and certain limitations exist when it's possible to do so e.g., non-Finnish users may access the chipster service via EGI. However, this has limited features, and so access to the whole service may be granted only if a user purchases access to CSC's servers. Another example is the Finnish Social Science Archive (FSD), where cross-border consumption may be permitted for researchers affiliated with Finnish research organisations or if the data has a focus on the Finnish society.
- Latvia has included services that are only cross-border, i.e., all the services are open for cross-border consumption and collaboration, but the HPC service is not free of charge.
- A majority of the Swedish compute services are not open to cross-border usage, however a Swedish researcher might collaborate with international research colleagues. One of the smaller compute services is open for both cross-border consumption and collaboration. Both of the data analysis services are open for cross-border consumption but not collaboration. One of the data storage services is not open for cross-border consumption.

Cross-border collaboration is allowed

Figure 8: Cross-border collaboration by country

⁴ <https://prace-ri.eu/hpc-access/deci-access/>

Cross-border collaboration is allowed

Figure 9: Cross-border collaboration.

Regarding the commercial usage it differs between the countries, see figure 10.

- The services from Iceland are not available for commercial usage.
- Up to 20% of the resource capacity (HPC/storage) can be used by commercial customers in Norway.
- In Denmark, the services are generally available for commercial use, but availability is limited to national institutions in the research and educational sector.
- In Estonia, 6 out of 13 services can be used by commercial entities. In some cases, usage is evaluated case by case.
- In Finland, all except one service can be used for commercial purposes. However, some limitations apply.
- Academic services listed by Latvia can be used by commercial companies if open R&I is considered (results of research/work are made public). Usage for purely commercial purposes are limited and EC regulations for 20% of resource capacity also apply for EU funded hardware/service.
- Usage for purely commercial purposes is limited for the Swedish compute services as well as for the security and identity services. For one of the data storage services, it's not prohibited but not encouraged either. Otherwise, the other services can be used for commercial purposes.

Figure 10: Commercial usage by country

Commercial usage is allowed

Figure 11: Commercial usage.

The countries differ from each other when it comes to the services that are free for academic use.

- The services from Iceland are free for academic use.
- All services from Norway except TSD (service for sensitive data) are free for small-scale academic projects. Larger projects have to contribute to the operations of the e-infrastructure. This model may change in the future.
- Only 20% of the Danish services are available for free for academic use.
- About 75% of the listed services in Estonia are free for academic use. Only compute services are not free for end users. It does not matter if they are academic or commercial.
- In Finland, CSC's chipster service is available to non-Finnish academic users via collaboration with EGI. The other services from CSC are not freely available for non-Finnish academic users. The data services by Tampere university (Aila data service and FSD) are available freely for all.
- In Latvia, the computing services are not free of charge (pay-per-use is applied) but other services listed are free with some limitations.
- A majority of the services in Sweden are free for academic usage in the same country, but the percentage is lower regarding academic usage outside of the country. One of the Swedish compute services and a data storage service is not free for academic usage outside of the country.

The image below (figure 12) shows that services can be funded from a variety of sources, including national instruments, research projects, the EU and the industry. The green arrows show the money flow the services are funded through and they might also be charging for their services.

Figure 12: Service providers & usage.

Access policies in use

Access to the services⁵ are generally remotely accessed or virtual, with only one service accessed physically, see figure 13.

⁵ EOSC Provider Portal - Resource Profile | EOSC Portal (eosc-portal.eu), <https://eosc-portal.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC-Profiles-v3.00.pdf>

Access Policies in use

Figure 13: Access policies.

- The services from Iceland are remote. For the HPC service the researchers and teachers can apply for themselves (and their graduate students) for free access. For the data storage it's open access for free for non-profit use.
- All services from Norway are accessed remotely via the Internet.
- Only one service in Denmark is done by mailing and all the other services are available online.
- In Estonia, 11 out of 13 services are accessed remotely, and 2 can be accessed virtually.
- All the services in Finland are available virtually through the internet.
- For Latvia, all the services are accessible from the web and are stated as remote.
- One of the services in Sweden is accessed physically the rest are accessed virtually or remotely.

Service TRL

The majority of services, 73,8% (45 services) are at TRL9. The remaining services are at TRL8 (8 services) or TRL7 (7 services). TRLs of two services were unknown (N/A), see figure 14.

Service TRL

Figure 14: Service TRL..

- The services from Iceland are at TRL 9.
- All considered services from Norway are at TRL 9.
- The danish resources are all at TRL 9 level except one at TRL7 and one n/a.
- In Estonia, 1 service has TRL7, 4 services are at TRL8 and 8 services are at TRL9.
- All services from Finland are at TRL9.
- In Latvia, the services range from TRL7 to TRL9, consistent with Beta to Production
- The services in Sweden range from TRL7 to TRL9, consistent with Beta to Production.

The figure below (figure 15) shows the difference between the countries.

Service TRL & Countries

Figure 15: Service TRL by country.

Service phase

Service phase

Figure 16: Service phase.

- The service phase for the services in Iceland are production.
- All mapped services from Norway are in production.
- All the services in Denmark are in production except one.
- In Estonia, all services are in production phase, except one, which is a new service and in beta phase.
- All services in Finland are in production.
- Latvian services are in production, with the ones stated as beta being close to production.
- A majority of the services from Sweden are production, and two are beta.

Service phase & countries

Figure 17: Service phase by country.

In conclusion, the majority of the services are in production with a minority end of life or planned to start or beta, see figure 16 and figure 17.

Service language

- The service language in Iceland is English.
- All services from Norway are available in English.
- The service language for services in Denmark are in English. Two services are in Danish because they only cater to a national and Danish speaking audience.
- All services in Estonia are available in English, and most of them are available in the national language as well.
- All services in Finland are available in English, with one data service available also in Finnish, and another also in both Finnish and Swedish.
- Latvia has services both in English and Latvian, but some parts of service might not be translated to English.
- Three services in Sweden are in Swedish and two of them are for national use only. However, most services are available in both Swedish and English.

As a conclusion, the services can be used by English speaking users, though the services can in some cases not be fully translated or may be intended for national use only.

Terms of use

- Iceland: The terms of use are not available for the HPC service and are available for the data storage service but are for the organisation and not for the specific resource.
- For all mapped services from Norway, the terms of use are available via web pages.

- In Denmark, there are terms of use for all of the services.
- In Estonia, only 5 out of 13 services have the terms of use ready and published.
- All the Finnish services have the terms of use available online in different formats (documents, web pages etc)
- Latvia has terms of use for all TRL9 services but not for those under TRL9.
- For some of the services in Sweden, the terms of use are stated not for the specific resources but for using HPC in Sweden. For some of the services, terms of use are not applicable. The rest have terms of use for a specific service.

Privacy policy

- Iceland's is available with a link but is for the organisation and not for the specific resource.
- For each service from Norway its privacy policy is available via a web page.
- In Denmark, there are privacy policies for all of the services.
- In Estonia, only 5 out of 13 services have privacy policy documents ready and published.
- Privacy policies for all except one Finnish service are available online.
- Latvia has privacy policies for all TRL9 services but not under TRL9.
- The majority of the services in Sweden have privacy policy, however for some it's not applicable.

User guide manual

- In Iceland, there are user guide manuals available with links for both services.
- User guide manuals are online available for all Norwegian services.
- In Denmark, there are user guides manuals for all of the services.
- In Estonia 11 out of 13 services have user manuals publicly available.
- All the Finnish services have the user guides available online.
- Latvia has most of the user guides online.
- The majority of the services in Sweden have user guide manuals, however for some it's not applicable.

Lessons learned and discussion

In this section we focus on several aspects:

- Value - Value is the importance or worth of the services mapped.
- Structural hindrance - is relating to the way in which parts of a service are arranged that make it more difficult to do something or for something to develop.
- Structural drivers are related to the way in which driving forces impact a service that facilitates development locally, nationally or internationally.

Value

What value can the mapping of services bring to the service providers?

The value to the service providers rests on the advantage the service provider achieves by listing their service on the EOSC-Nordic's regional portal or on the EOSC portal. Such a value must be even greater if it is to minimise the burden and cost of conducting an actual onboarding to EOSC-Nordic or EOSC ecosystems. The value achieved might be in the form of increased exposure of the service to potential user

communities, increased service consumption and/or a stamp of approval by a relevant or trusted entity and increased network ability.

Very few of the mapped services have been identified as catering to a substantial amount of cross-border consumption. Some services have the potential of achieving cross-border consumption, while others do not have the potential of achieving cross-border consumption. For instance, the mapping in Denmark indicates that the burden and risks of achieving significant cross-border consumption far outweigh the benefits. Therefore, an identification and assessment of the drivers and inhibitors for cross-border consumption observed by the services seems highly relevant. Cross-border consumption in Sweden is mostly available for community services. On the other hand, good examples of cross-border collaboration is for instance LUMI, which has its major funding from the EU and also from the participating countries. Also, from a top-down perspective - LUMI is an example of ensuring a cross-border set up efficiently - the cost models and technical availability were solved between the countries in an efficient way.

Structural hindrance

National by design - Most of the mapped services have been developed to cater for needs at their home institution or at the national level. This has in many instances made the services national by design. If a service is national by design, the time and cost of making the service accessible and relevant for cross-border use may be substantial or even prohibitive.

No international mandate for the service - Many of the mapped services are developed and maintained locally by National Research & Educational Networks (NRENS) or individual universities or research projects. These institutions are typically mandated to cater for users at the national or institutional level. If these institutions are to make the effort and have the cost of making the service cross-border, they will typically not be able to find this in their local mandate. To make it cross-border, the effort therefore might have to "fly under the radar". The national interest tends to lead to a national design of the service, the interest drives the services to design it for a national use and it can be a cost- and resource issue for the national services to add on a cross-border use, since there is no cost coverage for such a task. If a service caters for a national interest, then the service usually has national restrictions on usage, language or other integrations that makes the service impractical or unusable for cross-border use. There are also regulations and policies that make the service impractical or unusable for cross-border use. There is also an issue of the nearness of the service, a service might be close by to use for a user in their own country or university.

A service is bound to the local language - Services that have been developed and maintained as a collaborative effort will typically conduct their collaboration through their local language. When this is the case, the user documentation, legal terms and even change management processes also tend to be in the local language. While these may be translated, it is seldomly sufficient to do this as a one-off process. The future maintenance of such documents will induce costs if they are to be maintained in the local language and English.

Funding and staffing are local - In an ideal world, tasks and responsibilities would be placed where they are most efficiently executed. Institution A might possess the best engineers and should therefore maintain the data center and institution B in a neighbouring country might possess the best administrators and should be tasked with management and user engagement. In practice, this is seldom done due to inherent inertia in outsourcing responsibilities and control outside one's own institutions. The support work load and financial predicaments would increase in order to offer a service in a European context.

Commercial usage is generally accessible to all but it's a complex issue. Services need to be economically attractive for academia. There are also restrictions for academic usage through public procurement and research funds held in reserve.

Structural drivers

Economies of scale: If a service wants to grow to a certain size in order to cater for new functionality, consumption types and so on, the service might need to cater to users outside its institution or national community. An example of this would be a simple repository or compute service, that wants to attract users currently using commercialised services. If such a service wants to achieve similar costs and scalability, a certain scale would be necessary, and this would unlikely be achieved at the national level. Free for academic use is a complicated issue, and is determined by different legal, national, institutional and funding rules. The reason the services are for free is that it is a national (or institutional) interest to have them freely available, but it adds extra issues regarding cost/VAT and national regulation.

Supporting specialised research: In many fields of research the number of skilled researchers is limited and will likely be mostly found abroad. This is particularly the case with relatively small research communities in individual Nordic countries compared with for instance the US or China. Some specialised research fields like Arctic research or fauna in the Baltic sea may have special relevance to Nordic researchers who may also require specialised and advanced (expensive) services. The cost of financing such services might be prohibitive unless it is executed at the Nordic level.

Supporting popular cross-border services: Increased political support of cross-border services with high visibility can have a high probability of valuable outcomes and a low risk of failure. In such cases a cross-border service may be decided upon through a top-down effort. Such a service may be viable even when the participating institutions are unable to present a positive business case for the effort. Positive examples of this are for instance LUMI and MAX IV.

Use of existing mandated cross-border institutions: Several successful cross-border procurements have been performed through Nordunet, NeIC and GÉANT. The most recent example is the Amberscript framework contract by Nordunet. This allows Nordic users access to transcription and subtitling services for research and educational institutions. Here the service is available in the Nordics but still governed at the national level through the national NREN. This may limit the cost and lift the quality of performing such tasks across the Nordics. The service facilitates cross-border collaboration amongst managers, but it does not facilitate cross-border collaboration for researchers with the actual media files that are being processed.

Harmonisation of services - There is no clear path for the services on how to work out harmonisation and synchronisation of the services so that users can expect equal service, terms of use, interface, support and language. Harmonising services can be an objective with best practises for resource providers aiming to facilitate convergence within the EU for service provisioning, hence making it easier for users. This also corresponds to the *Knowledge base* developed in WP6⁶

The image below (Figure 18) aims at illustrating both the large diversity concerning (cross-border) usage approaches and funding sources for services. The majority of services is developed and operated through national funding programmes, and most use (in terms of capacity) of them is limited to users from the country which provides funding to these services (circles labelled "National use only" and segments of other circles NOT intersecting with the EOSC circle). However, many services can be, and are already, being used across borders via EOSC or other means (fraction of blue circles intersecting with the EOSC circle). What fraction of these services is being used across borders may vary from service to service. The development of the EOSC platform itself is funded mostly by the European Commission. So, there seems to be a dilemma of many services being potential candidates for the EOSC platform, but their funding prohibits

⁶ <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/knowledge-hub/>

their full exploitation across borders. At the same time, EOSC seems to focus solely on developing the platform for resource exchange. To demonstrate the full potential of EOSC, it may be necessary to enable EOSC to provide significant resource capacity by itself. A fast means could be that EOSC buys service capacity from services which is then made available to cross-border usage. This could also motivate service providers to onboard more of their services to EOSC.

Figure 18: Diversity - Cross-border, usage, and funding.

Conclusion and next steps

Only a few services in the mapped Nordic-Baltic inventory currently allow cross-border usage. However, count of such services is slowly increasing due to rising demand for cross-border consumption. There are examples of cross-border collaboration, however they are mainly financed cross-border with a specific target, i.e., are not financed through generic research funding schemas.

Identification and assessment of the drivers and inhibitors for cross-border consumption observed by the services seems highly relevant and can be investigated further. We have found that the services' main drivers consist of national interest and laws/regulations and financial input. This makes harmonisation more difficult.

A possible objective for EOSC in the future would be to assist the services to mature further. Assistance can consist of guides on best practises and discussions on how to improve the services. This would also enhance the EOSC network and the onboarding process of services.

Services with EU funding should be able to fulfil the EOSC guidelines and requirements. It would make services interesting for researchers to use when they are approved by EOSC and add value to the researchers' unique contexts. A stamp of approval from EOSC would mean that researchers can find mature and reliable services. With the stamp coming from a trusted partner (EOSC), it would increase the credibility and value of the services.

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